

Myths & Barriers to Insulin Therapy in the patients of Diabetes Mellitus

Masooma Hashmi, Farid Adnan, Abdul Wasey Hashmi, Izzah Khalid

ABSTRACT

Objective: Diabetic Patients in Pakistan are either hesitant to use Insulin or have poor compliance. There are numerous misconceptions and barriers to using insulin for the control of blood sugar leading to late adaptation often leading to complications of Diabetes mellitus.

The aim of this study was to determine the barriers to Insulin Therapy and the myths associated with poor compliance of insulin therapy in patients with Diabetes Mellitus.

Study design: A cross sectional conducted at Sakina Institute of Diabetes & Endocrine Research (SiDER), Shalamar Hospital, Lahore.

Methodology: The study was conducted using questionnaires, designed separately for patients using Insulin, and for those not using Insulin, to determine the barriers to initiation and poor compliance to Insulin therapy.

Results: Out of the 124 patients that participated in our study, 58.9% of these were those who never used Insulin, while 41.1% were on Insulin therapy. Among the patients not using Insulin, about 71.4% expressed their fear of taking Insulin because of the pain from injections; 83.4% felt that self-administration of Insulin is a discouraging factor because of the procedure; 61.9% felt that cost of Insulin therapy is a huge barrier to its use and 78.6% were reluctant in using Insulin, because they feared it would make their life less flexible. Among the patients using Insulin, about 62.7% were satisfied with their lifestyle; 84.3% said they adapted well to the route of administration and 64.7% felt an improvement in their health status after starting taking Insulin. Nearly, 80.4% of the patients currently using Insulin, were reluctant to initiate Insulin therapy; and about 66.7% said that proper information and counselling from their physicians helped them make the decision of starting Insulin and, 19.6% admitted to being motivated by their Family/Friends.

Conclusion: Numerous myths and barriers exist, resulting in reluctance among patients of Diabetes Mellitus to comply with insulin therapy. However with appropriate counselling from physicians and stimulus from the patient's family and friends helped them to start Insulin therapy with proper compliance.

Key words: *Insulin, Diabetes Mellitus, Myths, Barriers*

INTRODUCTION

As predicted by the World Health Organization, there will be a rise of 170% in the incidence of Diabetes Mellitus in the developing countries, with an estimated patient population of 228 million.¹ Hence, the developing countries will account for as much as 75% of the Diabetic population by year 2025.² It is for this reason, important that we identify the different barriers in the diabetic patients of developing countries about Insulin therapy, which is the best treatment of this disorder. It is also important then, to remove these barriers for improving the compliance of patients to Insulin.

Ahmed et al did a study comprising of 317 Muslim diabetic patients at Aga Khan Hospital, Karachi, of whom 55.8% were males. In the study group, 210 patients never used Insulin. They found out the barriers to Insulin therapy using a questionnaire. About 72.9% felt that Insulin is the last resort in their treatment and 45.2% indicated a fear of development of tolerance to Insulin. Only about 45.7% felt that Insulin therapy would reduce the known complications of Diabetes Mellitus. While, 24% thought that Insulin therapy would

interfere with religious obligations. When questioned about Insulin administration, 34% thought that Insulin administration is difficult to learn, 41% felt that they could not self administer Insulin, even in an emergency situation and, 25% completely refused to take Insulin under any circumstance. The study also found an association of lack of education with these identified barriers. Among 107 patients on insulin, 52.3% were reluctant before the initiation of therapy while, 78.5% felt an improvement in their glycemetic control and 86% said they will recommend insulin therapy to diabetic patients.³

In a research by Mass. General Hospital, Boston, about 33% of Type 2 Diabetics were unwilling to initiate Insulin therapy. The most commonly felt barriers in these patients about insulin were concerns about developing hypoglycaemia, permanent dependence on Insulin, less dosage flexibility and fears of failure of therapy. About 40% expressed fear of self injection and though that injections were painful. The researchers compared this data with the willing patients under the same study and concluded that, unwilling patients were fearful of injections and the associated pain, a less flexible lifestyle. These barriers resulted into a poorer general health and higher depression scores in these patients.⁴

Kunt et al studied barriers to initiation of insulin therapy, in patients of diabetes. They said that, health care

Correspondence: *Dr. Masooma Hashmi*

Demonstrator

Department of Community Medicine

CMH Lahore Medical College and Institute of Dentistry

Lahore

Email: masooma.hashmi@gmail.com

professionals face many hindrances from patient's side, to Insulin initiation in primary care. The most common of these barriers according to Kunt at el were low motivation, lack of familiarity with the methods of Insulin administration and certain time constraints.⁵

In a US study by Rubin et al, some barriers in patients using Insulin were identified. They found out that, majority of these patients wanted to reduce the number of injections they take each day; nearly half of the study group said that they would comply fully to their insulin dosage, provided they could be given some product to reduce the pain associated with injections. A relatively smaller number of patients thought of injections as a serious burden. They were dissatisfied with the injectable form of insulin, as according to them, it had a negative impact on their quality of life, and hence skipped their regular insulin dosages many times.⁶

The objective of this study is to identify different myths and barriers to Insulin Therapy in the patients of diabetes mellitus at Sakina Bibi Institute of Diabetes & Endocrine Research (SiDER).

METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted in patients with diabetes mellitus presenting to Sakina Begum Institute of Diabetes & Endocrine Research (SiDER), Shalamar Hospital in Lahore. Two questionnaires/surveys were designed for this purpose; (1) for patients not taking insulin and (2) for patients currently on insulin therapy.

The study group consisted of patients, ≥ 20 years of age and diagnosed with Diabetes Mellitus. The questionnaires were in English language. Patients were helped by research coordinators to understand the nature of the questions, asked. Only those patients were included who consented to participate in the study. The study was carried over a period of two weeks. Around one hundred and forty eligible patients were approached and 124 consented to participate. Patients who were seriously ill or who had any cognitive impairment were excluded from the study. Health care providers and those patients who refused to participate were also excluded. The identity of the patients and their questionnaire responses were kept confidential. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS version 20.

The questionnaires were developed in house and modified before use in the study. The two questionnaires were not identical. Demographic data was collected and questions pertaining to the status of Diabetes were also asked. All questions were close ended, and were used to determine the factors which are responsible for the barrier in Insulin therapy, among the patients of Diabetes Mellitus. Emphasis in this study was to determine; the barriers among the patients not taking Insulin and the impact of Insulin therapy on the patients who are taking

it. The questionnaire for the patients who were not taking Insulin was divided into two parts; patients who were fearful of initiating Insulin therapy were made to answer questions pertaining to the reasons for their fear, and the patients who were to initiate Insulin therapy who were not apprehensive about Insulin were asked questions on the factors responsible for their lack of fear.

RESULTS

Of the 124 patients, who participated in the study, 73 (58.9%) were those who never took Insulin and, 51 (41.1%) were on Insulin therapy. Among the 73 patients who never took Insulin, 42 (58%) reported having fear of using Insulin therapy in the future and, 31 (42%) said, they do not have any fear regarding the use of Insulin, and are willing for Insulin therapy, if advised by their physicians. (Fig. 1) The range of age of participants who were on Insulin Therapy was 35 years to 80 years ; of participants who never used Insulin but were fearful of the therapy was 22 years to 70 years and those who never took Insulin and were not fearful of the Insulin therapy was 20 years to 70 years. The gender ratio for patients taking Insulin was 41 (80.4%) females for 10 (19.6%) males; it was 29 (69%) females for 13 (31%) males for those not taking Insulin, but fearful and, was 19 females (61.3%) for 12 (38.7%) males for the group who never took Insulin and wasn't fearful as well. (Figure. 2)

Factors that interfered with regular usage of insulin were also assessed. Those who missed the doses were asked about the factors responsible for skipping/missing of the doses of Insulin, and about 56.9% said that, cost of Insulin is high and sometimes unaffordable, and they skip the injections; 17.6% said that pain from injections is a hindrance; 15.7% stated that due to certain social commitments, they sometimes miss the doses; stigma was a hindrance in 2% of these patients; 3.9% skipped doses due to fear of side effects and, about 3.9% skipped Insulin doses for having freedom from Insulin Dependence. (Table 1.2)

Almost 80% of patients taking insulin stated that they were reluctant about initiating insulin therapy. We asked these patients about the factors that motivated them to start taking Insulin and these are shown in Table 1.3.

Out of the 73 patients who were not on insulin therapy, 42 said they were fearful for initiating insulin therapy, whereas, 31 were not fearful. Response generated from the first group (n=42) is shown in table 2.1.

The patients not taking insulin and fearful of insulin therapy were also asked about oral hypoglycemics.

The reasons given by patients for considering oral hypoglycemics as a better treatment option are shown in Table 2.2.

Fear Status - Non Insulin Patients

■ Fearful of insulin The rapy ■ Not Fearful of Insulin The rapy

Figure 1: Fear Status – Non Insulin Patients

Figure 2: Gender Distribution

Table 1: Response generated from Patients Taking Insulin

Question	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Are you satisfied with your lifestyle post insulin initiation?	32	62.7	19	37.3
Do you feel that Insulin has reduced your clinical symptoms of DM?	32	62.7	19	37.3
Have you adapted to the route of administration of Insulin?	43	84.3	8	15.7
Are you adequately trained in self administration of Insulin?	42	82.4	9	17.6
Do you use Insulin regularly without skipping the prescribed dosage?	30	58.8	21	41.2
Do you think Insulin has or will reduce the complications of DM?	33	64.7	18	35.3
Will you recommend Insulin therapy to other patients?	37	72.5	14	27.5
Do you think, you will develop tolerance to Insulin?	21	41.2	30	58.8
Do you feel any stigma associated with Insulin usage?	15	29.2	36	70.6
Were you reluctant about Insulin therapy, before its initiation?	41	80.4	10	19.6
Are your views about Insulin therapy influenced by anyone suffering from DM?	34	66.7	17	33.3
Are you satisfied with your overall health post initiation of Insulin therapy?	32	62.7	19	37.3

Table.1.2: Reasons/Hindrances to the REGULAR usage of Insulin

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cost	56.9	56.9	56.9
Pain from injection	17.6	17.6	74.5
Social commitments	15.7	15.7	90.2
Stigma	2.0	2.0	92.2
Fear of side effects	3.9	3.9	96.1
Freedom from Insulin Dependence	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.3: Motivating Factors for the Group taking insulin

	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Self motivation	9.8	9.8	9.8
Doctor/Physician	66.7	66.7	76.5
Family/ friends	19.6	19.6	96.1
TV/ other media	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Table 2.1: Response generated from Patients Not On Insulin and Fearful of Therapy

Question	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you have any fear of pain from injection?	27	71.4	12	28.6
Will you ever take Insulin?	8	19	34	81
Do you think self administration of Insulin is difficult?	35	83.4	7	16.6
Do you fear a lifelong dependence on Insulin?	37	87.7	5	12.3
Do you think Insulin is the last resort treatment of DM?	30	71.4	12	28.6
Do you think Insulin will make your life less flexible?	33	78.6	9	21.4
Do you think taking Insulin will deteriorate your health?	26	61.9	16	38.1
Do you think of it as a lifelong burden on economy?	26	61.9	16	38.1
Do you think, taking Insulin will complicate your case?	24	57.2	18	42.8
Do you fear having hypoglycaemia (side effect of Insulin)?	28	66.7	14	33.3
Do you think taking Insulin will interfere with your religious obligations?	10	23.8	32	76.2
Do you think you will develop tolerance to Insulin?	24	57.2	18	42.8
Do you feel any stigma associated with Insulin therapy?	26	61.9	16	38.1
Are your views about Insulin influenced by anyone suffering from DM?	28	66.7	14	33.3

Table 2.2: Reasons for considering oral hypoglycemics a better treatment option

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cheap	7	16.6	16.6	16.6
Oral route is convenient	16	38.1	38.1	54.7
Will not complicate my case	6	14.3	14.3	63
Flexible lifestyle & dosage	4	9.5	9.5	78.5
Hope of a good prognosis or cure	3	7.1	7.1	85.6
Less dependence	5	11.9	11.9	97.5
Feeling of having a better health	1	2.4	2.6	100.0
	12	100.0		

Table 3: Response generated from Patients Not On Insulin and NOT Fearful of Therapy

Question	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you think taking Insulin will reduce the complications of DM?	28	90.3	3	9.7
Will you ever take Insulin?	24	77.4	7	22.6
Do you think taking Insulin is convenient in terms of lifestyle & health?	20	64.5	11	35.5
Are you aware of the benefits of Insulin in patients of Diabetes?	19	61.3	12	38.7
Do you think the sooner you start Insulin therapy, the better it is?	19	61.3	12	38.7
Are your views of Insulin, influenced by anyone suffering from DM?	17	54.8	14	45.2

Out of 73 patients not on insulin therapy, 31 of them claimed that they were not fearful of insulin therapy. The response generated from these patients is shown in Table 3. When asked about the source of information of these patients, which helped them overcome the myths and barriers to Insulin therapy, about 58.1% (18) gave credit to their physicians/doctors for providing them with useful information about the disorder and Insulin therapy; 12.9% (4) said, they obtained information from the internet; 25.8% (8) said that, they were guided by their family and friends and only 3.2% found TV/Other forms of Media to be useful.

DISCUSSION

The dilemma of the developing countries or where resources aren't enough, insulin therapy is delayed and, the compliance is low because of certain myths and barriers associated with the use of Insulin, which result in a poor glycemic control.⁷ Sometimes, such views are derived from religious norms, social or cultural reason and, many a times, they are self-created.

It is important to address the issues related to Insulin therapy among the patients of Diabetes Mellitus, considering the ever increasing burden of this disorder in our society and, to improve the palliative treatment until, any cure is sorted out. In a UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) Group study, it was evaluated that more than half of the patients of DM will require Insulin therapy, after about 5 to 6 years from diagnosis, regardless of the oral hypoglycemic agents used.^{8,9,11}

In our study, lifelong dependence on Insulin therapy was found to be the commonest barrier. It was because the patient, were aware that, there is no cure of Diabetes Mellitus at present and only a lifetime monitoring is the only option.⁴ Another myth identified, is that a good percentage of patients thought of Insulin as the last resort option, primarily because they had previously seen patients being prescribed Insulin, just before experiencing a major complication such as leg amputation, nephropathy, neuropathy or blindness and sometimes, even death.⁵ Development of complication of vital organs in patients of Diabetes Mellitus, is also considered to be a popular misconception.¹² One of the most important barriers was considered to be the pain from injections of Insulin, which barred a sizeable

percentage of patients from starting or keeping up with the Insulin therapy^{6,10} It is suggested that about 58% of patients suffering from Diabetes Mellitus believed that, taking Insulin means that their previous therapy has not been beneficial.⁷

About, an estimated 33.3% physicians postpone the Insulin therapy until, it was found to be absolutely essential.⁷ It was also depicted in our study that, physicians played the most important role in educating their patients about the benefits of Insulin therapy. About 66.7% of the patients in our study taking Insulin said that, they were motivated by their Physicians and, in patients not currently taking Insulin, about 58.1% believed that their physicians helped overcome the fear of Insulin therapy.

In a study by EDIC, it was proved that earlier start of Insulin therapy ensured better prognosis and reduction in complications.¹³ About, 61.3% of patients in our study group, not currently on Insulin and not fearful as well, believed the same. However, 38.7% of this group had a different opinion. In 58.8% of the patients taking Insulin, who admitted to skipping/missing doses of Insulin, certain factors were identified including cost, pain of injection, social stigmata etc. Cost of Insulin therapy was found to be the most prevalent barrier among this study group. It is primarily because of the low socioeconomic status of the residents of South East Asia. Pain from Injection (17.6%) and Social Commitments (14.7%) followed cost, as important barriers to Insulin therapy.

Our study also identified stigmata associated with the use of Insulin therapy as a barrier. They believed that, diabetics were somewhat unacceptable and unwelcomed at a certain stage and, weren't considered as normal. Restriction and control of dietary intake and regular monitoring made them feel uncomfortable. Some patients also reported of getting irritated by the overt concerns of their family all day long, about their food intake and, pushing them for exercise. A small barrier interfering with Insulin therapy was religious obligations, among Muslims, particularly in the Holy Month of Ramadan when concerns about hypoglycaemia and Insulin therapy arise due to fasting.

However, despite all these it was noted that patients who were reluctant about the Insulin therapy (80.4%) at first,

later adapted well to the change and were found to be satisfied as per our study (62.7%). Proper guidance by the doctors/physicians and information on the benefits of Insulin therapy motivated these patients to start Insulin therapy, and combined with support from family and training of the patients on the usage of Insulin therapy were the factors which helped them keeping up conveniently with Insulin therapy. Hence, low motivation and lack of familiarity with the method to inject Insulin are important barriers to Insulin therapy.⁵ Hence, it is important that we provide quality and bias free health education to our people about the benefits of Insulin, in order to clear the minds of our patients about any myths, barriers or misconceptions associated with Insulin therapy. It will help, in achieving the target glycemic goals of the patients of diabetes mellitus already on Insulin and, will address to the pertaining hesitations of patients in starting Insulin therapy.

CONCLUSION

Myths, Barriers and Misconceptions regarding Insulin therapy among the patients of Diabetes are prevalent in our society, but they can be dealt with/eliminated by educating the patients about the benefits of Insulin. It was also noted, that the opinions and views regarding Insulin therapy significantly improved after patients were put to Insulin therapy.

REFERENCES

1. Guariguata L, Whiting DR, Hambleton I, Beagley J, Linnenkamp U, Shaw JE. Global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2013 and projections for 2035. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2014 Feb 1;103(2):137-49.
2. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H. Global prevalence of diabetes: estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030. *Diabetes care*. 2004 May 1;27(5):1047-53.
3. Ahmed US, Junaidi B, Ali AW, Akhter O, Salahuddin M, Akhter J. Barriers in initiating insulin therapy in a South Asian Muslim community. *Diabetic medicine*. 2010 Feb;27(2):169-74.
4. Larkin ME, Capasso VA, Chen CL, Mahoney EK, Hazard B, Cagliero E, Nathan DM. Measuring psychological insulin resistance. *The Diabetes Educator*. 2008 May;34(3):511-7.
5. Kunt T, Snoek FJ. Barriers to insulin initiation and intensification and how to overcome them. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*. 2009 Oct;63:6-10.
6. Peyrot M, Barnett AH, Meneghini LF, Schumm-Draeger PM. Insulin adherence behaviours and barriers in the multinational Global Attitudes of Patients and Physicians in Insulin Therapy study. *Diabetic Medicine*. 2012 May;29(5):682-9.
7. Khunti K, Wolden ML, Thorsted BL, Andersen M, Davies MJ. Clinical inertia in people with type 2 diabetes: a retrospective cohort study of more than 80,000 people. *Diabetes care*. 2013 Jul 18;DC_130331.
8. UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) Group. Intensive blood-glucose control with sulphonylureas or insulin compared with conventional treatment and risk of complications in patients with type 2 diabetes (UKPDS 33). *The Lancet*. 1998 Sep 12;352(9131):837-53.
9. Wright A, Burden AF, Paisey RB, Cull CA, Holman RR. Sulphonylurea inadequacy: efficacy of addition of insulin over 6 years in patients with type 2 diabetes in the UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS 57). *Diabetes care*. 2002 Feb 1;25(2):330-6.
10. Young-Hyman D, De Groot M, Hill-Briggs F, Gonzalez JS, Hood K, Peyrot M. Psychosocial care for people with diabetes: a position statement of the American Diabetes Association. *Diabetes care*. 2016 Dec 1;39(12):2126-40.
11. UK Prospective Diabetes Study Group. UK Prospective Diabetes Study 16: overview of 6 years' therapy of type II diabetes: a progressive disease. *Diabetes*. 1995 Nov 1;44(11):1249-58.
12. Heisler M, Vijan S, Makki F, Piette JD. Diabetes control with reciprocal peer support versus nurse care management: a randomized trial. *Annals of internal medicine*. 2010 Oct 19;153(8):507-15.
13. For the Diabetes Trial, Control and complications Trial/Epidemiology of diabetes interventions and complications research group. Sustained effect of intensive treatment of type 1 diabetes mellitus on development and progression of diabetic nephropathy: the epidemiology of diabetes interventions and complications (EDIC) study. *JAMA: the journal of the American Medical Association*. 2003 Oct 22;290(16):2159.